

APPENDIX IN MODERN ENGLISH

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Abstract: In this article, scientific-theoretical opinions about the application phenomenon in English today were conducted..

Keywords: Application, method, foreign language, text, devices, oral speech, grammatical form

It is known that special attention is paid to learning a foreign language in Uzbekistan. The role of a foreign language in training highly qualified specialists in higher educational institutions is incomparable. The main goal of language learning is to develop the habit of speaking in a foreign (English) language. Modern pedagogical technologies are very useful in the realization of this goal. At present, the role of qualified personnel in the development of Uzbekistan is huge. In particular, journalists are trusted to convey the reality of the world to the public.

It has a scientific value for the science of English stylistics, including writing scientific articles on the topic of stylistic analysis and comparison of artistic works in English and Uzbek languages, as well as creating training manuals, as well as special courses on this topic in higher educational institutions. can be used to pass courses. Structural analyzes are of scientific and practical importance not only for English stylistics, but also for the modern Uzbek literary language.

A number of issues related to stylistics remain the cause of debate when studied not only by Uzbek scholars, but also by English scholars. One such contentious, problematic issue is about app elements.

1. In modern English literature, the phenomenon of attachment is a widespread stylistic phenomenon. There are various structural types of the application device. . Now, the application device phenomenon is a topical issue in various languages as a syntactic-stylistic phenomenon. In terms of structure, the application device is divided into two large groups.

2. Applied elements expressed without connecting links. Conjunctive elements are expressed by connecting conjunctions. It is the relevance of the topic to study and analyze the additional elements that have been expressed with the help of these connectives and without them.

In English linguistics, this situation is studied as a stylistic phenomenon. The case of the adjunctive device occupies an important place in modern English

syntax. English scientists G. Shtarke, U. Khoberk, L. Shpiser and others explain the attachment device in the construction of the sentence by such terms as deviance, alienation, combination, division or expanding the idea. As a result of the review of scientific literature, it can be concluded that the phenomenon of application device is a characteristic of the English language.

1. *Application devices have the following features:*

2. *Simple or compound sentences are stopped (pause) in oral speech, and through a period in writing;*

3. *these parts through grammatical and semantic connection with each other;*

4. *two-piece component;*

The separated element is separated by expressing and describing the main event. An adjunctive event is a fragmented presentation of an idea without additional phrases. An opinion expressed after a period is an additional expression to the main expression in the sentence:

Some adjuncts also look like incomplete sentences. Sentences in the application device depend on the main expression, which expresses the idea expressed by one person and shows the unity of information:

According to the nature of the meaning, the applied elements express the same meaning of the grammatical tense. Morphologically, the grammatical categories of the verb in the application device, such as mood, person, number, must match, otherwise it becomes an elliptical sentence. It is also possible to switch the position of the sentences in the application, in which case the grammatical sequence does not change.

If the number of appended elements attached to the main expression is one, then a simple structural appendage is a device. By complex structural application device, we mean a construction with more than one application elements connected to the main expression.

It should be noted that in the function of an adjunct, not only phrases can appear, but also complete sentences, connected clauses, and subordinate clauses.

The application device event initially occurred during the speech process. Intonation plays an important role in this. In written speech, intonation is determined by a dot. According to N.S. Pospelov, tone plays a key role in the connection between the main expression and the additional element. Many scientific works have been conducted to study this. Tone, which is of great

importance in oral speech, is also manifested in written speech, and it is marked by a dot when expressing additional elements.

It should be noted that sentences with an adjunctive element have a lowering of the voice and a slight stop with a tone.

The use of different adjunctive constructions in one case or another depends of course on the purpose of the person speaking or writing. Because the additional element is used to add meaning to the previously mentioned idea and to strengthen the meaning of this idea. Therefore, this phenomenon should not be understood as a phenomenon that occurs suddenly and secretly only in the process of oral speech. It should be noted that the application device phenomenon is also widespread in written speech and it depends on the personal style of each writer. widespread in the literature.

Application elements can perform various stylistic functions within the application device. Their stylistic functions are mainly to simplify the sentence structure and increase the effectiveness, artistry, liveliness of the described events; the depicted event - increasing the effectiveness, artistry, liveliness of events; the described event - drawing the reader's attention to the event, etc. We intend that our observations on these works will be the main factor in the future comparative study of similar phenomena occurring in the works of this or that writer. The results of the work can be widely used in the process of reading analysis, in practical training in the science of stylistics, as well as in the theoretical and practical science of translation.

The application has characteristic features that can be divided into three large groups: syntactic, semantic and pragmatic. *Syntactic properties of applications:*

❖ *All applications can be divided into applications that perform a nominal function and applications that do not perform a nominal function. The first group includes role-playing applications.*

❖ *The application and the word being identified may belong to the same or different syntactic classes. Since most applications perform a nominative function, most applications and defined phrases are expressed in substantive phrases. (noun phrase/NP).*

❖ *The word being used and defined are usually adjacent, but there are also cases where they are separated by other parts of the sentence.*

In conclusion, we can state the following that adjunctive constructions are a unique syntactic phenomenon that fulfills the function of an expression that appears as an addition, they are called an adjunctive element according to their structure. This additional element clarifies and develops the meaning of the

main expression (main sentence), explains it to a certain extent. Such syntactic structures usually consist of two parts, the first part represents the main information, and the second part represents the additional message.

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